

Defects in nanoporous Au: insights from variable energy positron Doppler broadening studies

C. Lakshmanan*, R.N. Viswanath, R. Rajaraman, G. Amarendra, C.S. Sundar

Materials Science Group, Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research,
Homi Bhabha National Institute, Kalpakkam 603 102, Tamil Nadu, India
cml@igcar.gov.in / 09445532970

Abstract

The analysis of low energy positron beam experiments in terms of positron diffusion and positronium fraction, $f_{3\gamma/2\gamma}$ provides an opportunity to obtain information about positron annihilation behaviour and depth-wise defect distribution in nanoporous solids such as nanoporous Au (1). Herein, we have applied the positron beam with energy E , in the range of 0.2-21 keV to study the positron diffusion behavior in nanoporous gold, having two distinct states, positively charged as-dealloyed and electrochemically reduced. It has been revealed from the analysis of the positron annihilation γ -ray spectra that the positronium fraction, $f_{3\gamma/2\gamma}$ with E in as-dealloyed nanoporous Au and bulk Au is found to be the same, whereas that obtained in reduced nanoporous Au is significantly increased (c.f. Fig. 1c). The increased positronium fraction, $f_{3\gamma/2\gamma}$ in reduced nanoporous Au is due to the absence of repulsive potential felt by the diffusing positrons at the surface of Au ligaments.

Keywords: electrochemical dealloying; nanoporous gold; slow positron; positronium fraction

Fig. 1: a, b) Typical scanning electron microscopy images of positively charged as-dealloyed and electrochemically reduced nanoporous gold respectively. c) Positronium fraction $f_{3\gamma/2\gamma}$ vs. positron incident beam energy E , for as-dealloyed (\circ), electrochemically reduced ($*$) nanoporous Au and defect free bulk Au (Δ).

Reference

1. C. Lakshmanan et al, EuroPhys.Lett., 117, (2017)48007.